

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Simeon

FIRST NAME: Akinjobi

PROGRAM CODE: DGEF

COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Academic or scholarly written essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7)
2. Punctuation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15)
3. Variants of World English: American & British (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024, P.33)
5. When citing references would not be necessary (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 37)

REVIEW OF ACA-401D PERIOD 1 COURSEPACK

1) INTRODUCTION

It has been a dream come true for me to register and start my PhD program to registered and start my PhD program finally. After many years of procrastination and some financial setbacks.

Since I registered, I have encountered some difficulties navigating through the start-off. Some applications on my laptop are also not helping matters as they are different from those seen in the videos and instructions provided.

But, with persistence and help from current students on the WhatsApp group, I have been able to progress.

2) GUIDE TO WRITING GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

According to the authors - Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma there are many types of essays, but the focus of the reading was on academic essays. Academic essays are usually nonfiction and are scholarly written.

There are many features that distinguish academic essays or scholarly written essays from others. But one feature that stands out for me, as described by the authors, was the fact that “Academic essays seek to provide an answer(s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7).

To help with some guidance in writing an essay, some steps have been highlighted by the authors to guide accordingly, like an early start-up, defining the question and analyzing the task, and drafting an initial plan.

3) PUNCTUATION

As demonstrated by the authors, it is critical that the writer keep the following procedures.

- Know all the punctuation marks and their usage
- Learn the examples of how punctuation marks are used
- Differentiate between correct and incorrect punctuation

Various examples were given in terms of some common punctuation marks like apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colons and semicolons, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipses, full stops, exclamation marks, question marks, and quotation marks.

4) VARIANTS OF WORLD ENGLISH: AMERICAN & BRITISH

Since the end of World War II, we have seen significant growth in the use of American English. This is explained by tremendous development and positivity around America’s economy. Some of the points noted by Cleenewerck and Gulma include -

1. Increase in US population
2. Increase in US wealth and economy
3. Increase in US higher education compared to the UK
4. Increase in publishing companies in the US
5. Increase in media industry and media technological advancement in the US
6. World acceptance of US’s culture, language and way of life
7. The US has a significant position in world politics and economy.

According to Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 34-36), some of the general categories of difference between Standard American English (SAE) and Standard British English (SBE) include the following.

1. Different Pronunciation, Although Same Spelling
2. Different Spelling, Although Same Pronunciation
3. Same Term, Different but Similar Spelling and Pronunciation
4. Same Words, But Different or Additional Meanings
5. Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation, General Usage
6. Differences in Usage with SBE 'Large Collective Nouns'
7. Differences in Usage with SBE 'Pluralised Adjectives'

There are so many of them, but I have only mentioned a few.

5) **PLAGIARISM**

The section on plagiarism centered on what it is and how to avoid it, knowing how to cite appropriately with paraphrasing, and some guidance around inserting footnotes using MS Word.

Rightly described by Cleenewerck and Gulma, plagiarism is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34).

Any act of copying, citing, or describing other people’s ideas or works without attributing due credit to the author is plagiarism. To avoid this, whenever the works of others are cited or referenced, the author must be mentioned appropriately.

Sometimes for me, I found it difficult in some cases not to copy other people’s ideas and work. But the rule is that it is permissible as long as the work, ideas, etc., are appropriately referenced and credited to the author.

However, there are instances when citing or quoting would not be necessary. This would be when the word is a piece of common knowledge. “For example, smoking causes lung cancer. There is no need to cite since it is well known that smoking causes lung cancer” (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 37).

6) **CONCLUSION**

Going by the last time I finished my master’s degree programme and was involved in serious academic work, this period at EUCLID has been somewhat tough, though. This was coupled with new things like Zotero I needed to learn.

I guess this first period has mentally prepared me for what is yet to come. I have also realized that to complete the program successfully, I would need to put in more extra effort.

With the support of my Supervisor, Dr. Kabiru, I am so sure I would navigate through successfully.

REFERENCE

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.